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REPORT ON PATHWAY
DEFINITION

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About this report

This report describes the process for the definition of EU energy transition pathways developed in REEEM and introduces the structure, main assumptions and preliminary impact indicators of the first pathways defined. It addresses different groups of readers, specifically 1) the general audience, since it presents in a transparent fashion the methodological and modelling framework developed in REEEM, 2) the European Commission, through its explicit link with the Energy Union and the SET-Plan, 3) energy modellers and modelling projects, in that it delivers a scientifically sound and repeatable process to define pathways for a multi-model and multi-sectoral analysis, 4) stakeholders, since it pinpoints the steps in the REEEM activities where interaction with them is essential and explains how it occurs, 5) the REEEM partners, in its guiding the modelling teams towards the creation of an integrated modelling framework and the continuation of the quantitative analyses.

The methodology and this related report are a joint effort of all the partners involved in REEEM Work Package 1 (Transformation strategies and pathways).

REEEM partners

About REEEM

REEEM aims to gain a clear and comprehensive understanding of the system-wide implications of energy strategies in support of transitions to a competitive low-carbon EU energy society. This project is developed to address four main objectives: (1) to develop an integrated assessment framework (2) to define pathways towards a low-carbon society and assess their potential implications (3) to bridge the science-policy gap through a clear communication using decision support tools and (4) to ensure transparency in the process.

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1. Introduction

With the Europe 2020 Strategy first [1], followed by the Energy Roadmap 2050 [2] and finally the ratification of the Paris Agreement, the EU has committed to a medium- to long-term transition to a low-carbon and competitive economy. This implies, amongst others, the decarbonisation of the energy system.

While the motivation and the goal of the energy transition are clear and generally agreed upon within the EU, the way they should be accomplished is veiled by uncertainty. A long-term plan for transforming the energy system is needed and, therefore, decisions must be taken today with a future vision.

Model-based analyses emerged as a tool for energy system planning since the oil crisis in the 70s, when mathematical methods were formulated to indicate pathways for reducing the consumption of oil and increasing the efficiency of energy processes. Since then, a wide number of analytical tools to support energy planning was developed. They are generally structured to simulate and/or optimise the behaviour of entire systems, taking into account the interdependency between their elements and the variety of stakeholders affected by the planning. Through these tools, decision-makers can gain understanding of the possible implications of planning decisions and elaborate resilient energy plans consequently.

The International Energy Agency (IEA) summarised the phases of the model-aided energy planning process as in Figure 1 [3].

Figure 1. Phases of an energy planning process.

The process can be essentially divided in three main phases: the first one is devoted to preparing the model-based analysis and retrieving insights for the decision makers, the second where decisions informed by the outcomes of the analysis are taken and implemented and the last one where iterations are made if necessary.

The REEEM project is collocated in the context of the first phase. It carries out a model-based analysis of the impacts of policy measures and transformation pathways to a sustainable EU energy system. Specifically, the analysis aims to gain understanding of the role and the (social, economic and environmental) impacts of energy technologies in the transformation pathways to a low-carbon and competitive EU energy system. The employed modelling framework is a complex ensemble of more than 15 tools with a system-wide perspective (including climate-energy-water-land nexus, macroeconomic, energy, LCA, emission dispersion, emission impacts, technology development and behavioural models).

Therefore, the activities of the project revolve around the definition of these transition pathways, intended as internally consistent and comprehensive pictures of how the energy system could evolve and which technologies could play a key role.

This report describes the methodology developed by the REEEM Consortium to define transition pathways to a low-carbon EU energy system and introduces the first decarbonisation pathways defined within the activities of the project. The methodology recalls phase 1 of the process shown in Figure 1, Section 2 synthetically introduces the key terminology employed throughout the work; Section 3 proposes a review of scenario and pathway definition approaches; Section 4 describes the pathway design process and analyses it step-by-step; Section 5 briefly discusses aspects of the pathway diagnostics; Section 6 presents a preliminary modelling exercise carried out in REEEM; Section 7 concludes with a brief discussion.

2. Terminology

Future: used in REEEM to define one possible future overall ‘State of the World’ in a broad and qualitative way. It provides a context for the analysis.

Scenario: used in literature in the same way as ‘future’.

Narrative: used in REEEM to define a short qualitative description of a future.

Pathway: used in REEEM to represent an energy transition process within one future. In practical terms, it is a collection of numerical assumptions and numerical outputs of the models.

Technology issue: within every future, the pathways are clustered according to the specific technology issue they look at. In REEEM, a technology issue is a specific theme, linked to the development of a family of technologies.

Diagnostic indicators: used in REEEM to define quantitative metrics derived from the outputs of the models and giving a numerical representation of the social, economic or environmental impacts of each energy transition pathway.

3. Scenario and pathway definition in literature

In the long term energy modelling practice, scenarios are often used to reflect future uncertainties. Especially, they find application as exploratory or assisting techniques to shed light on the available choices and their potential consequences. The scenarios can be defined as internally consistent illustrations of plausible futures [4]. These can, in turn, be converted into quantitative collections of modelling assumptions and results, which we call in this report *pathways*.

Scenarios can be broadly classified into descriptive and normative [5,6]. These two classes usually give different messages and therefore target different audiences. Descriptive (or exploratory) scenarios investigate how the future might unfold when certain processes take place. Normative scenarios investigate how given outcomes or objectives might be met.

A distinction can be made also in the approaches to the definition of scenario and pathways, in particular between top-down and bottom-up approaches [7]. A top-down approach moves from a plausible, internally consistent and broad image of the future and scales it down into a number of pathways; a bottom-up approach explores a solution space by changing the modelling assumptions and creating one pathway for every set of assumptions. Then it identifies the scenario which each pathway may be consistent with.

A review of a few energy modelling exercises where scenarios and pathways have found application follows.

The Special Report on Emissions Scenarios (SRES) by the IPCC presents four scenarios, described by narratives illustrating the relationships between the main economic, demographic, and technological driving forces of global GHG emissions [8]. Making different assumptions on the driving forces, such as the rates and trends in technological change, different economic-development pathways are developed. Each pathway consists of a specific quantitative interpretation of one of the four broad narratives. All the pathways based on the same storyline constitute a pathway 'family'. A total of 40 SRES pathway is developed using a multi-model framework. Thirteen of them explore variations in energy technology assumptions.

The World Energy Council (WEC) elaborates two scenarios, one focusing on mitigation through high level of cooperation between countries and one focusing on adaptation through decentralised decisions and markets [9]. Within these two scenarios, a wide pathway space is explored, in order to improve the understanding of future uncertainties over global energy use. The pathways of this exercise are descriptive and belong to the same category as the IPCC's SRES. Once again, the taxonomy of the scenario development process starts from an overarching rationale related to governance models. Then, the GMM model is used and a wide range of possible energy technology portfolio options is explored, by varying the assumptions over the main driving forces that affect each technology.

Shell's New Lens Scenarios [10] qualitatively describe the unfolding of two plausible alternative futures and their impacts on the demand for energy carriers and energy services. The main difference between the two futures lies on the diversity of the stakeholders involved in the decision making. The study indicates that the more inclusive the decisional processes are, the slower the implementation of governance models may be. The demographic, economic, social and environmental implications of the two futures are discussed and insights into the possible portfolios of winning technologies within each of them are given.

In 2014, O'Neill et al. elaborated the narratives for the Shared Socioeconomic Pathways (SSPs) [11]. This study follows a slightly different approach to those mentioned above. The scenarios are defined by combinations of mitigation and adaptation challenges. Within each of them, the pathways explore different levels of challenges deriving from dynamics internal to the society, with a normative approach.

In the Global Energy Assessment, a single normative scenario of the transition towards a sustainable future is assumed, setting the societal and political framework of the exercise [12]. Within this scenario, a number of pathways is defined, with a normative approach. Each of them pursues different sustainability objectives and assessing the technological and economic feasibility of the strategies to meet them.

The Energy Roadmap 2050 by the EC starts by asking how the objectives of sustainability, competitiveness and security of the EU energy system can be met [13]. Four groups of technology development routes potentially answering this focal question are analysed: energy efficiency, renewable energy, nuclear energy, and carbon capture and storage. These may be called *technology issues*. These routes are combined in different ways to create seven scenarios for 2050. These scenarios are then turned into pathways including assumptions on a wide portfolio of technologies, the role of consumers and investors, a specific regulatory framework.

Following a similar approach, an extensive technology portfolio analysis is performed also in the EMF27 studies. At the highest level of the scenario development process, three objectives related to sustainable technological development are set, namely decarbonisation of the energy supply, increasing use of low-carbon energy carriers in end-use sectors, and reduction of energy use. The pathways are then differentiated according to the implementation of strategies related to these elements and their timing.

This overview shows that a wide variety of approaches for the formulation of energy transition scenarios and pathways has been developed in literature and applied globally as well as to the EU energy system. Summarising the main characteristics of the approaches, two considerations can be made:

- In model-based energy systems analyses, it is common practice to combine scenarios, qualitatively describing the broad context, with pathways, collecting modelling inputs and outputs to provide the quantitative picture.

- Deep discussion takes place in literature about the involvement of stakeholders in the scenario definition process and different ways are proposed to ensure it.

Also a number of unresolved questions emerge:

- Diverse and non-uniform terminology is used in different exercises. In an attempt of summarising the uses of a few key words, we could point out that: a) the word scenario generally represents an overarching picture of a state of the world; b) the word pathway generally expresses an energy transition process within one scenario. The two words might nonetheless be confused, if not appropriately framed.
- At times, it is complicated to map the whole process leading from the formulation of the scenario to the collection of the numerical assumptions fed as inputs to the models. This is more relevant when 1) numerous models are employed and soft- or hard-linked in the analysis, 2) a multi-sectoral analysis is carried out.
- In exercises focusing on technological development within the energy system, scarce if no reference is made to how the numerous Technology Roadmaps available in literature, resulting from intensive consultations with stakeholders especially from industry, can be linked to the definition of energy system transition scenarios.
- The suitability of a specific approach depends on the purpose of the analysis and the target audience. However, in multi-sectoral analyses involving a number models, both traditional top-down or bottom-up approaches may be liable to misalignment between the overarching storyline and the numerical modelling assumptions, undermining the internal consistency of the analysis.
- There is not a best approach between the descriptive and the normative, but they may be employed alternatively, depending on the kind of focal question to be answered and the intended recipients of the scenario exercise.

With the process for defining pathways described in this report, the REEEM project proposes solutions to these questions. The main characteristics of the process are listed below:

- 1. The use of the word “scenario” is avoided, while a clear definition of pathway is given and employed.*
- 2. A process for the definition of pathways is structured and mapped step-by-step from the conception of a future state of the world to the collection of numerical assumptions for the models.*
- 3. The link with the Technology and Innovation Roadmaps elaborated in REEEM is identified and the entry points for stakeholders at different steps of the process for defining the pathways are highlighted.*

4. Overall, the proposed process for defining the pathways can be seen as **top-down**. However, one of the first steps of the process consists in choosing the families of technologies for which the role and impact is to be assessed.
5. No descriptive or normative perspective is assumed a priori, but rather introduced a posteriori, varying the sets of modelling assumptions.

4. Pathway definition in REEEM

In REEEM, a modelling assessment is being undertaken to explore a diverse set of *low carbon transition pathways*, providing insights to a range of stakeholders impacted by the Energy Union [14] and Integrated Strategic Energy Technology (SET) Plan [15], namely *decision makers*, *market actors* and *consumers*. Different stakeholders have a set of different priorities which the scenario framing used in the modelling needs to satisfy or inform.

For instance, the policy makers may be interested to look at metrics indicating how the societal costs are minimised, how the total welfare is maximised and whether there is societal acceptance, when different technologies are introduced in the European energy system with or without certain policy measures. For technologies that are not profitable yet, but have high societal benefits, the policy makers may decide to implement policies to speed their adoption.

The market actors may focus on the possible penetration, operability and profitability of one technology when a number of uncertain parameters related to the maturity of the market are varied.

Finally, it may be useful for consumers to see metrics regarding the return on investment of different end-use energy technologies or options for the active participation to the market, their impact on the final energy prices and their environmental footprint.

The next subsections detail the methodology and describe its application.

4.1. Overview of the process

Figure 2 provides a graphical representation of the process for defining pathways under the scope of REEEM.

The process is divided in four main parts, each composed by several steps: definition of the future (top-left), choice of the technology issue (top-right), definition of the pathway (lower branch), consistency check (bottom). These parts and the individual steps are described in the following subsections, with the objective of making the process repeatable in other long-term energy system modelling and planning exercises.

Figure 2. Process for the definition of pathways in REEEM.

4.2. Definition of the future

As briefly introduced before, in REEEM a *future* represents one possible ‘State of the world’ and it is defined in a systematic way via the so called morphological approach [16]. In this approach, the world is described by various *dimensions* (capturing for instance Political, Economic, Social, Environmental and Global factors). Each of these dimensions could play out in multiple ways, described by different *states*. Therefore, a future represents one plausible, unified and consistent picture of how the different dimensions could play out. The following subsections detail how the steps to define futures were carried out in REEEM.

The steps of the process devoted to the definition of the future are highlighted in Figure 3. They were carried out by project partners, with involvement of stakeholders through different activities which are described in detail in the following subsections.

Figure 3. Definition of the future.

4.2.1. Step 1a: define matrix of dimensions and states

This step was carried out in REEEM by the partners involved in WP1 (Transformation strategies and pathways) during a number of internal workshops and brainstorming sessions. The dimensions were chosen making reference to numerous similar exercises in literature. The states for each dimension were chosen based on the knowledge of how the future might unfold. In particular, the states of the political dimension are inspired by the European Commission’s White Paper on the future of Europe [17], while those of the other dimensions come from observation of the numerous debates ongoing in the EU and global arena. The first matrix elaborated in REEEM is shown in Table 1. It will be discussed and extended by stakeholders (with addition of states) during the first REEEM Stakeholder Workshop, in October 2017.

Table 1. Matrix of dimensions and states in REEEM.

Political [A]	Economic [B]	Social [C]	Environmental [D]	Global [E]
Stronger union post-Brexit, common policy framework, push to decarbonisation [A1]	Strengthening EU economies [B1]	Strong societal engagement [C1]	High availability of water and scarce resources [D1]	RCP2.6 and global R&D push to climate change mitigation [E1]
Cooperation only between groups of countries [A2]	Uneven EU growth [B2]	Passive society in transition [C2]	Low availability of water and scarce resources [D2]	RCP4.5 and strong global reliance on fossil fuels to support growth [E2]
Low cooperation, protectionism and self-reliance, priority on national security [A3]	Increased regional disparity, more exposed to Euro crises [B3]			

4.2.2. Step 2a: decide a rationale

In order to obtain a full picture of the future, the working group had to choose one state for each dimension and combine them in a consistent fashion. A rationale, or criterion, was needed to choose and combine the states. In REEEM the partners decided to use as a rationale the degree of cooperation between Member States, due to its centrality in the current debates and the potential impact on the transformation of the energy system. Therefore, their choice of the states started from the political dimension. They created two alternative futures by choosing two opposite states, both deemed possible (A1 and A3). Then, states for each of the other dimensions were chosen consistently.

4.2.3. Step 3a: define future

The two alternative combinations of states chosen by the REEEM partners constitute two futures. The first one represents a situation following from a renewed spirit of cooperation between the Member States, which allows for the establishment of a common and solid policy framework for the decarbonisation of the energy sector. It is named *Together on a low-carbon path* and it is presented in Table 2. The second one moves from a spirit of diffidence and self-reliance, which leads to a more fragmented policy framework in several sectors, including energy. It is named *Trusting paradigms of the past* and it is presented in Table 3.

Table 2. Combination of states for the future: *Together on a low-carbon path*.

Political [A]	Economic [B]	Social [C]	Environmental [D]	Global [E]
Stronger union post-Brexit, common policy framework, push to decarbonisation [A1]	Strengthening EU economies [B1]	Strong societal engagement [C1]	High availability of water and scarce resources [D1]	RCP2.6 and global R&D push to climate change mitigation [E1]
Cooperation only between groups of countries [A2]	Uneven EU growth [B2]	Passive society in transition [C2]	Low availability of water and scarce resources [D2]	RCP4.5 and strong global reliance on fossil fuels to support growth [E2]
Low cooperation, protectionism and self-reliance, priority on national security [A3]	Increased regional disparity, more exposed to Euro crises [B3]			

Table 3. Combination of states for the future: Trusting paradigms of the past.

Political [A]	Economic [B]	Social [C]	Environmental [D]	Global [E]
Stronger union post-Brexit, common policy framework, push to decarbonisation [A1]	Strengthening EU economies [B1]	Strong societal engagement [C1]	High availability of water and scarce resources [D1]	RCP2.6 and global R&D push to climate change mitigation [E1]
Cooperation only between groups of countries [A2]	Uneven EU growth [B2]	Passive society in transition [C2]	Low availability of water and scarce resources [D2]	RCP4.5 and strong global reliance on fossil fuels to support growth [E2]
Low cooperation, protectionism and self-reliance, priority on national security [A3]	Increased regional disparity, more exposed to Euro crises [B3]			

A large number of possible futures can be questioned, i.e. a large number of combinations of how the six dimensions could play out. More futures will be defined during the first REEEM Stakeholder Workshop in October 2017.

4.2.4. Step 4a: write a narrative for the future

Following the definition of the two futures, the working group in REEEM conducted the corresponding narratives. The narratives are intended to be the entry point of stakeholders to the whole pathway exercise of REEEM.

Together on a low-carbon path

In this future, a stronger EU emerges from the Brexit negotiations, with a renewed sense of cooperation between the Member States in a number of policy domains, including immigration, fiscal, social, public health and taxation matters. As a result, in the wake of the Paris Agreement, EU28 agrees on a common policy framework regarding climate change mitigation, the decarbonisation of the energy system and the deployment of renewable energy sources. Efforts are shared to complete a single European energy market and upgrade the network infrastructure. While the cooperative framework and the clear EU-wide policy setting provide a more secure environment for investments, the fact that decision-making processes are centralised sometimes makes them slower.

A period of economic growth, rather evenly spread across EU28, begins after the crisis. Common frameworks, diminishing competitiveness gaps and fewer barriers help the economies approach convergence. The EU carries out trade agreements with other regions with a single voice, thus ensuring markets of goods, services and also primary resources. Within the EU28, an open and well-regulated market of energy (e.g. fossil resources and biomass) is guaranteed. Such a market has to operate under scarcity of water and rare materials in some regions.

Worldwide, the Paris Agreement drives large scale investments in clean technologies, including renewables, in a strong attempt to mitigate climate change. This, in turn, drives fast development and cost decrease of such technologies also on the European markets. EU28 takes advantage of the favourable environment for clean energy technologies development and becomes a front runner of the decarbonisation of the energy system, creating a solid policy framework for investments in renewables and low-carbon technologies. This provides a ground for potentially reducing the material intensity of the energy sector.

Thanks to joint investments in innovation and research, a fertile environment for venture capitalists, start-ups, large companies and research centres is created across the EU. Fully integrated capital markets help mobilise finance for small and medium enterprises and major infrastructure projects across the EU. Consequently, progress is made in the development of clean tech industries, both on the supply and consumption side.

The more centralised and at times slower decision-making processes may cause suspicion and detachment among part of the society, which therefore engages less in the challenges of the transition to a low-carbon energy system. The strong and common regulation on energy technologies and sources at EU28 scale fills the gap, providing specific directives to every Member State.

Trusting paradigms of the past

Brexit, the absence of an agreed view on migration and the uncertain political environment give rise to a spirit of self-reliance and protectionism across the Member States. The main priorities of the political stage become national economy, use of local resources and energy independence. Consequently, EU28 re-sizes its ambitions and re-centres its priorities only around the single market. Policies in all the other fields, including energy and climate, are left to Member States and often dealt with through bilateral agreements. While this means in many cases faster decisional processes, it also implies fragmentation of the policy framework, including the one set by the Paris Agreement. While the decarbonisation targets for EU as a whole remain in place, some of the Member States renegotiate the national targets, potentially affecting other countries.

The monetary union and the free movement of capital persist, but with reduced political cooperation, growing divergence in growth between regions, and therefore increased vulnerability to new financial shocks. Trade agreements are left to bilateral negotiations. An additional constraint lies on the scarcity of water and rare materials in some EU regions.

Worldwide, the Paris Agreement drives large scale investments in clean technologies, including renewables, in a strong attempt to mitigate climate change. This, in turn, drives fast development and cost decrease of such technologies also on European markets. However, the penetration of different renewable and fossil fuelled technologies in the Member States is uneven, since it also depends on the policy framework established by each of them, the local availability of cheap fossil fuels, the security of investments and the behaviours of consumers.

A share of the citizens, variable in each country, not seeing the desired progress on energy and climate policies at the national and international level steps up and assume a more active role in promoting the transition to a lower-carbon and energy efficient society. A more active role includes a higher participation in the countries' political debate and low-carbon consumer choices. However, the rest of the citizens keep living their daily life without much attention to the energy and climate landscape.

4.3. Choice of the technology issue

In parallel with the formulation of the futures and independently from it, the technology issue was chosen. This part of the process consists in two steps, as shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4. Choice of the technology issue.

4.3.1. Step 1b: list possible technology issues

Again, this step was carried out in the first place by the project partners. The stakeholders will be involved during the REEEM Stakeholder Workshop in October 2017, providing an entry point especially for decision-makers at the EU level to point out which technology development tracks it might be useful to look at.

The REEEM working group decided on a list of technology issues. These make reference to the challenges of the Integrated SET-Plan, described in the Strategic Energy Technology Plan Progress report 2016 [18]. The five technology issues chosen so far by the REEEM partners are reported below, including information on the technologies they focus on:

- **Technology issue 1: EU number 1 in renewables.** Focus on: electricity and heat storage technologies, grid connection to adjacent markets, flexible energy supply technologies, innovative renewable energy technologies;
- **Technology issue 2: efficient and smart energy system.** Focus on: energy efficiency measures in residential buildings, energy efficiency measures in heating and cooling industrial processes, synergies with other energy networks like gas and CHP;
- **Technology issue 3: centralised and secure supply.** Focus on: nuclear power plants, Carbon Capture and Sequestration (CCS);
- **Technology issue 4: Consumers at the centre of a decentralised energy system.** Focus on: electricity and storage technologies, smart metering, distributed Renewable Energy Sources (RES), load shifting, load shedding and other demand-side services;
- **Technology issue 5: sustainable transport.** Focus on: electric vehicles (EVs), hydrogen-fuelled vehicles, fuel cells for mobility, biofuels, hybrid vehicles, batteries for light and passenger and freight transportation.

The theme of the REEEM first Technology and Innovation Roadmap, elaborated by EIT InnoEnergy and to be submitted to the European Commission on July 31st, 2017, was chosen in accordance with the list of technology issues reported above and so will those of the following Roadmaps. Specifically, the first Technology and Innovation Roadmap analyses *electricity and heat storage technologies*, therefore providing useful inputs on technology issues 1 and 4.

4.3.2. Step 2b: choose a technology issue

After the list of all the technology issues is defined, for each of them a set of pathways shall be defined.

4.4. Definition of the pathway

Within a future and a technology issue, several pathways can be defined. As introduced before, in REEEM a pathway represents an energy transition process. In modelling terms, this is a collection of numerical assumptions and numerical outputs of the models.

One pathway is univocally defined by its numerical assumptions and outputs. If even one assumption changes, a new pathway is generated.

The part of the process dealing with the definition of the pathway consists of four main steps, shown in Figure 5. These steps require knowledge of the purpose, inputs and outputs of all the models. Since the modelling framework in REEEM involves not only one model, but numerous models of several sectors, the steps have to be carried out by all the modelling teams, coordinated by the leads of REEEM WP1 (Transformation Strategies and Pathways) and WP6 (Energy System Integration). The complexity and level of integration of the modelling framework marks a methodological and scientific breakthrough of the REEEM modelling activity.

Figure 5. Definition of the pathway.

A description of the steps follows.

4.4.1. Step 5: define the modelling framework

This step is the one most unveiling the complexity of a model-based pathway analysis involving numerous models and diverse spatial, temporal and sectoral coverage. In REEEM it was carried out by the leads of WP1 (Transformation Strategies and Pathways) and WP6 (Energy System Integration) and it involved continuous consultations between them and all the modelling teams. It consisted mainly of the following actions:

1. Collecting general information on all the models employed in REEEM and their sectoral coverage;
2. Collecting from the REEEM WPs where modelling activities are carried out information on: 1) all the modelling tasks to be carried out according to the Grant Agreement, 2) the models to be employed for each task and their geographic coverage, 3) the deadlines to deliver the results, 4) the time required for modelling, 5) the links between inputs and outputs of the models;
3. Including all the information collected in the qualitative description of the technology issues and elaborating a work plan.

Table 4 synthesizes the outcome of point 1 and lists all the models involved in REEEM and their sectoral coverage. More detailed information is available on the model factsheets published on the project website, reem.org.

Table 4. Modelling framework of REEEM.

Model	Sectoral coverage in REEEM
Pan-EU TIMES	Bottom-up energy system model
Pan-EU OSeMOSYS	Energy system engagement model including simplified characteristics of several others
MESSAGE	Bottom-up energy system model
ESME	Regionally disaggregated UK energy system model
Plexos	Short-term electricity dispatch model
NEWAGE	Global CGE model
EnergyPRO / EnergyPLAN	Models for energy sector planning
Ecosense	Linear model quantifying impact of emissions on health
EVA	Nonlinear model quantifying impact of emissions on health
EMC2	Model for the spatial allocation of emissions, starting from country-wide aggregated figures
CORDEX Database	Database from which the availability of water for energy use is retrieved, as a function of the climate scenario
LCA	Life Cycle Assessment of energy technologies and supply options

LEcA Tool	Model of the impact of the energy sector on the ecosystem services
Behavioural model	To be created upon the results of surveys to consumers

Table 5 synthesizes the outcome of point 2 and it shows the set of information collected from the modelling Work Packages is in REEEM, namely WP 2, 3, 4, 5 and 6.

Table 5. Synthesis of the information on the REEEM modelling framework collected from the modellers.

REEEM Task	Modelling framework / tool employed	Spatial coverage	Modelling activity (from – to)	Link to other models
Work Package 2 – Technology and innovation				
Task 2.4: case study on co-evolution of technologies	ESME	UK	Nov 2016 – Jan 2018	TIMES Pan-EU
Work Package 3 – Economy				
Task 3.3: model application, evaluation of results, policy recommendations	NEWAGE	Global, EU divided in 7 regions	Aug 2017 – Jul 2019	-
Task 3.4: case study on carbon leakage and competitiveness	NEWAGE	EU28+2, country by country	Jan 2017 – Jul 2018	TIMES Pan-EU
Work Package 4 – Society, consumers and behaviour				
Task 4.1: Role of individual actor behaviour and heterogeneity in the adoption of novel and energy efficient technologies	-	UK, Finland, Croatia	Feb 2016 – Jul 2018	(TIMES Pan-EU)
Task 4.2: distributional, societal and equity impacts of the SET-Plan	-	EU28+2	Jul 2016 – May 2019	TIMES Pan-EU and NEWAGE
Task 4.3: case study on district heating	EnergyPRO, EnergyPlan	Helsinki, Warsaw, Kaunas	Feb 2017 – Jan 2019	TIMES Pan-EU
Work Package 5 – Environment, health and resources				
Task 5.1: impact of climate change on the energy – land use nexus	-	EU28+2	Feb 2016 – Jan 2019	TIMES Pan-EU
Task 5.1: impact of climate change on the energy – water use nexus and on the heating and cooling demand	Cordex database	EU28+2	Feb 2016 – Jan 2019	TIMES Pan-EU
Task 5.2: health and environmental impacts from pressures to the environment	EcoSense, EVA, EMC2	EU28+2	Feb 2016 – Jan 2019	TIMES Pan-EU
Task 5.3: Life Cycle Assessment for energy systems and demand for critical materials	SimaPro	EU28+2	Jul 2017 – May 2019	TIMES Pan-EU
Task 5.4: case study on Ecosystem Services	LEcA tool	Lithuania	Jan 2017 – Jan 2018	TIMES Pan-EU

Work package 6 – Energy system integration				
Task 6.3: model application	TIMES Pan-EU	EU28+2	Feb 2016 – Jan 2019	NEWAGE
Task 6.4: case study on energy security of the Baltic region and Finland	TIMES	Lithuania	Feb 2017 – Jan 2019	TIMES Pan-EU
Task 6.4: case study on grid and dispatch in South Eastern Europe	PLEXOS	South-eastern Europe	Feb 2017 – Jan 2019	TIMES Pan-EU

From this information set, a graphical representation of the complete modelling framework of REEM is retrieved, as shown in Figure 6. The solid lines connecting items indicate established soft-links between modelling tools, where some outputs of one modelling tool are fed as inputs to another tool. The dashed lines represent potential feedback loops, not yet established and to be evaluated during the modelling activities. The red boxes represent models, while the yellow ellipses represent more generically analytical tools.

Figure 6. REEM modelling framework.

Finally, the outcomes of point 3 are shown below. For each of the technology issues listed in Step 1b, the same scheme as in Figure 6 is proposed, where only the models employed for the specific issue are highlighted.

Technology issue 1: EU number 1 in renewables. Focus on: electricity and heat storage technologies, grid connection to adjacent markets, flexible energy supply technologies, innovative renewable energy technologies.

Figure 7. Modelling framework employed for technology issue 1.

Technology issue 2: efficient and smart energy system. Focus on: energy efficiency measures in residential buildings, energy efficiency measures in heating and cooling industrial processes, synergies with other energy networks like gas and CHP.

Figure 8. Modelling framework employed for technology issue 2.

Technology issue 3: centralised and secure supply. Focus on: nuclear power plants, Carbon Capture and Sequestration (CCS).

Figure 9. Modelling framework employed for technology issue 3.

Technology issue 4: Consumers at the centre of a decentralised energy system. Focus on: electricity and storage technologies, smart metering, distributed Renewable Energy Sources (RES), load shifting, load shedding and other demand-side services.

Figure 10. Modelling framework employed for technology issue 4.

Technology issue 5: sustainable transport. Focus on: electric vehicles (EVs), hydrogen-fuelled vehicles, fuel cells for mobility, biofuels, hybrid vehicles, batteries for light and passenger and freight transportation.

Figure 11. Modelling framework employed for technology issue 5.

4.4.2. Step 6: collect numerical assumptions

Once the modelling framework to be employed for each technology issue is defined, the core step of the definition of a pathway starts, by collecting numerical assumptions. This step is carried out by the modellers, coordinated by the leads of WP1 and WP6, and it must be repeated for every new pathway.

The assumptions can be made for **uncontrollable** and **controllable** parameters. The **uncontrollable** parameters are those supposed to depend on dynamics not only internal to the EU, but also global, therefore outside the domain and control of the study. They include, for instance, swings in the prices of primary resources or uncertainties in the costs of energy technologies. The **controllable** parameters are those depending directly on decisions taken in the EU, such as national or EU policies, or investment decisions. Whenever introducing any assumptions in the following paragraphs, indication will be given on whether they refer to an uncontrollable or a controllable quantity. The importance of this distinction will be clearer in Section 5.

The collection of assumptions for every pathway in REEEM is carried out in the following order:

1. Assumptions depending only on the future;
2. Assumptions depending only on the future and the technology issue;
3. Assumptions distinguishing pathways within a future and a technology issue.

With this categorisation of the assumptions, once finalised, the list of all pathways shall look as illustrated in Table 6 (assuming for simplicity 2 Futures).

Table 6. Sample listing and naming of pathways.

Future (F)	Technology issue (TI)	Pathway (P)
F1	F1_TI1	F1_TI1_P1
F1		F1_TI1_P2
F1		F1_TI1_Pn
F1	F1_TI2	F1_TI2_P1
F1		F1_TI2_P2
F1		F1_TI2_Pn
F1	F1_TIn	F1_TIn_P1
F1		F1_TIn_P2
F1		F1_TIn_Pn
F2	F2_TI1	F2_TI1_P1
F2		F2_TI1_P2
F2		F2_TI1_Pn
F2	F2_TI2	F2_TI2_P1
F2		F2_TI2_P2
F2		F2_TI2_Pn
F2	F2_TIn	F2_TIn_P1
F2		F2_TIn_P2
F2		F2_TIn_Pn

All the assumptions made for all the pathways during the project will be collected on the REEEM Pathways Database. This is an open database, freely and publicly accessible upon registration (user ID and password are assigned by RLI on request), built in PostgreSQL-Server and hosted by the Technical University of Denmark, one of the REEEM partners. It contains all the main inputs and results of the pathways defined in REEEM and will be regularly updated by the modellers.

While this report is being finalised, the collection of assumptions for the first two full pathways is undergoing. The first pathway refers to *Future 1: together on a low-carbon path* and *Technology issue 1: EU number 1 in renewables*. The second pathway refers to *Future 2: trusting paradigms of the past* and *Technology issue 1: EU number 1 in renewables*. In the sample list of Table 6, the two pathways would be respectively F1_TI1_P1 and F2_TI1_P1.

In the following paragraphs, some of the main assumptions made for these two pathways are reported, divided in the abovementioned categories (1 - assumptions depending only on the future, 2 - assumptions depending only on the future and the technology issue, 3 - assumptions distinguishing pathways within a future and a technology issue). The full collection of assumptions for these pathways

will be available on the REEEM Pathways Database by January 31st, 2018 and it will be described in a section of the first REEEM Integrated Impact Report.

1. Assumptions depending only on the future

- **Decarbonisation targets.** The pathways analysed in REEEM are decarbonisation-oriented and thus decarbonisation targets will be assumed in all cases.

For every pathway within the future *Together on a low-carbon path* (therefore also for F1_TI1_P1), a target of 80% of CO₂ emission reduction in the energy sector by 2050 compared to 1990 is assumed for the whole of EU28+2, to be shared among the countries, according to the Energy Roadmap 2050 [2] (**controllable**). This is in line with the narrative of the future, describing a context of cooperation between EU countries, where the ground for common measures is solid.

In the future *Trusting paradigms of the past* (therefore also for F2_TI1_P1), a target of 80% of CO₂ emission reduction in the energy sector by 2050 compared to 1990 is assumed for each country in EU28+2 independently (**controllable**). This again aligns with the narrative of this future, describing a context where EU countries tend to issue policies independently, whether they are in favour of decarbonisation or not.

- **Population growth.** For every pathway within the future *Together on a low-carbon path* (therefore also for F1_TI1_P1), the population growth trends reported in The 2015 Ageing Report [19] are going to be assumed (**uncontrollable**). These are based on the same idea of a spirit of cooperation and openness in the future EU. The population trends are shown in Appendix A to this report.

In the future *Trusting paradigms of the past* (therefore also for F2_TI1_P1) the population trends need to be revised taking into account a more protectionist spirit of the EU countries. Values are not yet available.

- **GDP potential growth.** For every pathway within the future *Together on a low-carbon path* (therefore also for F1_TI1_P1), the population growth trends reported in The 2015 Ageing Report [19] are going to be assumed (**uncontrollable**). These are based on the same idea of a spirit of cooperation and openness in the future EU. The GDP trends are shown in Appendix A to this report.

In the future *Trusting paradigms of the past* (therefore also for F2_TI1_P1) the GDP trends need to be revised taking into account a more protectionist spirit of the EU countries. Values are not yet available.

2. Assumptions depending only on the future and the technology issue

For every pathway within Technology issue 1 – EU number 1 in renewables, a target of 75% of renewable energy share in the gross final energy consumption in EU28+2 by 2050 is assumed, in line with the *High Renewable energy sources (RES)* scenario of the Energy Roadmap 2050 [2]. With the same rationale as for the previous set of assumptions, two cases are possible depending on the future:

- For every pathway within the future *Together on a low-carbon path* (therefore also for F1_TI1_P1), the target is intended for EU28+2 as a whole, to be shared among countries (**controllable**);
- For every pathway within the future *Trusting paradigms of the past* (therefore also for F2_TI1_P1), the target is intended for each country independently (**controllable**).

3. Assumptions distinguishing pathways within a future and a technology issue

This set of assumptions accounts for those which are not fully determined even after choosing a future and a technology issue, because there remains a range of uncertainty over them even if the policy framework and the global context are set. They include, for instance:

- Capital and O&M costs of technologies not specifically targeted by policies or R&D efforts;
- Future trends of the emissions by unit of energy from technologies not specifically targeted by policies or R&D efforts;
- Level of subsidies to different renewable technologies within technology issue 1 (EU number 1 in renewables);

Pathways F1_TI1_P1 and F2_TI1_P1, and all the pathways which will follow, are tested against an *artificially constructed base case*, with no ground in any specific future or technology issue, employed solely as a term of comparison. This is built by:

- avoiding any assumptions (1) depending on the future or (2) depending on the future and the technology issue, and
- collecting techno-economic data for the third group of assumptions from reliable literature sources.

As it can be seen already from this example, part of the assumptions relates to techno-economic trends of specific energy generation technologies. The first REEEM Technology and Innovation Roadmap will contribute to these, by providing the expected techno-economic trends for selected heat and electricity storage technologies. These will be informed by literature, by the market outlook elaborated by EIT-InnoEnergy, and by experts' judgements.

Due to the number, detail and diversity of the models included in the REEEM modelling framework, the amount of this kind of assumptions is high. The full set will be available on the REEEM Pathways Database by January 31st, 2018 and it will be described in a section of the first REEEM Integrated Impact Report.

4.4.3. Step 7: run the models

This step is carried out by the modellers. For each pathway, each modelling team imports the assumptions collected on the REEEM Pathways Database, runs the models, obtains the results and exports the results again to the REEEM Pathways Database. Once the results are exported, the information on the pathway is complete and includes both assumptions and outputs of the models.

Some aspects deserve particular attention during this step:

- Many of the models employed in the REEEM modelling framework are linked, as shown in Figure 6. This means that the input assumptions of some models are outputs of others, thus the models cannot be all run at the same time.
- Some models share some input assumptions. Therefore, to ensure the modelling framework is consistent, those input assumptions must be harmonised to the highest possible extent.

The aspect of the links between models is out of the scope of this report. It will be discussed in the Integrated Impact Reports to be delivered to the European Commission in January 2018 and July 2019 and in peer-reviewed scientific papers by REEEM partners.

4.4.4. Step 8: synthesize the pathway

This constitutes the final step of the definition of a pathway. Once the assumptions and the modelling results of several pathways have been collected in the REEEM Pathways Database, the working group of Work Package 1 (Transformation strategies and pathways) will conduct reports including a synthetic description of the pathways, the main assumptions and results, the links to the relevant platforms for stakeholders to visualise them and the insights obtained.

4.5. Consistency check

The last part of the process is a consistency check. As shown in Figure 12, it is made of only one step, carried out by the modellers. This step constitutes a safety guard for the REEEM exercise. Given the complexity of the modelling framework, it might happen that the results of a pathway show unexpected trends and dependencies between some of the assumptions. When this occurs, the modellers and the leads of WP1 and WP6 may agree to define new pathways to carry out sensitivity analyses and investigate the causes of the unexpected results more in depth. In such cases, the whole pathway definition process will be repeated, as shown by the dashed line in Figure 12.

Figure 12. Consistency check.

5. Pathway diagnostics in REEEM

As mentioned in the previous sections, the pathway exercise carried out in REEEM aims at providing diverse stakeholders with understanding of the role and [economic, environmental and social] impacts of key energy technologies in the transition to a low-carbon EU energy system. Two sets of numeraires shall be employed in REEEM to this end:

- *Primary indicators*: they are the key direct outputs of each of the models employed, and they were selected by the REEEM modelling teams;
- *Secondary indicators*: they are derived from the primary indicators. In REEEM, a preliminary list of secondary indicators was created selecting among those commonly used in literature [20–27]. Stakeholders will have the possibility to add to this list during the second REEEM Stakeholder Workshop, yet to be planned.

The list of primary and secondary indicators currently employed in REEEM is presented in Appendix B. It will be modified and enriched during the whole modelling activity and the REEEM workshops.

As mentioned, the indicators are meant to provide understanding of the impacts on three dimensions, namely economy, environment and society. However, the distinction between these is not always clear and in literature the same indicator is often placed under different dimensions by different sources. Therefore, a preliminary suggestion is made in Appendix B on which dimension(s) each indicator could fit within, based on literature and on first indications by the partners. The list will be structured in ad hoc workshops within the Consortium and extended during the second REEEM Stakeholder Workshop.

Different groups of stakeholders, nominally policy makers, actors of the markets and consumers, will have access to all the indicators through an online, freely accessible Pathway Diagnostics Tool. This will be published by the 31st of January 2019. On the tool, stakeholders will be able to:

- Select pathways among those defined in REEEM, by selecting the values of the assumptions on **uncontrollable** or **controllable** parameters;
- Select which primary and/or secondary indicators to visualise and see their values over time on interactive graphs;
- Compare and rank pathways with respect to any of these indicators.

For instance, if a decision maker is interested to see the effects of a specific policy (in REEEM a controllable assumption), they may select the pathway through the corresponding **controllable** parameter, while keeping fixed all the others, and visualise the values of environmental, economic and social indicators. This corresponds to the one named in literature as **normative** viewpoint. On the other hand, if an actor of the market wishes to investigate the potential effects of price swings of primary resources (in REEEM an uncontrollable assumption) on the penetration of a technology in the energy system, they may select the pathway through the corresponding **uncontrollable** parameter while keeping the others fixed. This corresponds to a **descriptive** viewpoint.

As a further development, a multi-criteria decision framework will also be created in REEEM, where stakeholders can assign weights to chosen indicators from the environmental, economic and social dimension, so that a global score can be computed for each pathway.

6. A pilot thought experiment

This section describes an activity which was carried out in REEEM in parallel with the work on the pathway definition. Therefore, it does not fall within the process and the steps described in the previous sections, but it rather helped to define them.

As synthesised in Table 5, Table 6 and Figure 6, the modelling framework of REEEM is multi-sectoral and involves numerous models, developed and run independently by modelling teams in several institutions. Such comprehensive modelling framework constitutes the innovation of the project, but it also poses challenges:

- In order to define the pathways, assumptions for all the models must be made, they must be consistent across the models and they must be harmonised to the best possible extent;
- The results of the models must be synthesised in order to give transparent and coherent messages to the stakeholders;
- The models must be integrated, i.e. 1) flows of inputs and outputs between them must be established and 2) a rigorous modelling schedule must be established;
- Information must be preserved as much as possible when exchanged between models (what the sources of the data were, if and how the data was pre- or post-processed, what different names same parameters have, etc.).

These challenges can be addressed if an extensive and rigorously structured flow of information between the modelling teams is established. For this to happen, the modelling teams necessarily have to learn about the characteristics, inputs and outputs of each others' models and develop a common understanding of the possible links between them.

To this end, from the start of the REEEM project, a *Pilot thought experiment* was initiated, where the teams agreed to run their models on a common, loosely defined case study. To define this case study, each modelling team had the freedom to make their own numerical assumptions for nearly all the inputs, except for one: in accordance with the Climate Agreements, aiming at limiting the global temperature increase to 2°C, a target of 80% CO₂ emission reduction by 2050 compared to 1990 is imposed for the energy sector in the EU28+2. This assumption had to be shared by all the teams. In particular, two pathways were defined, based on it:

- Pilot 1. The 80% decarbonisation target is imposed to the EU28+2 as a whole and the burden shared between the countries.
- Pilot 2. The 80% decarbonisation target is imposed by every country of the EU28+2 independently.

Once this common assumption was agreed on, each modelling team carried out the following activities:

- Collection of the numerical assumptions of the model starting from internally available or commonly used datasets, even if not harmonised with other teams;
- Exchange of information with other teams regarding the structure, the inputs and outputs of the models, by sharing sample excel templates;
- Linking of the models where feasible.

The resulting modelling framework is depicted in Figure 13. A few mono-directional links were created, where the TIMES Pan-EU model feeds some of its outputs as inputs to other models. With respect to the previous analogue figures, an additional MESSAGE model for Lithuania is present, used as input to the LEcA Tool.

Figure 13. Modelling framework employed for the pilot thought experiment.

Up to present, results from TIMES Pan-EU, NEWAGE, EMC2, EcoSense and the Cordex Database for water use and heating/cooling demand were obtained, while the other tools were just calibrated.

The pilot is not built upon the rigorous process described in the previous sections of this report and does not narrate a fully consistent story about a plausible future state of the EU (many of the assumptions of the different models are not harmonised). Nonetheless, it fulfilled its scope of establishing a communication flow between the modelling teams and unveiling the challenges of the complex exercise undertaken in REEEM. Therefore, it provided the ground and material for constructing the pathway definition process described above.

In the following subsections, the main results of the pilot thought experiment are briefly reported, divided by model, with the sole aim of highlighting:

- What outputs can be expected of the different tools;
- What messages can be drawn by the comparison of two pathways, Pilot 1 and Pilot 2, with all assumptions in common except for the one on the EU wide vs national 80% decarbonisation target.

Finally, a discussion follows on the lessons learnt from the experiment.

The concept of the pilot thought experiment, its results and the lessons learnt were presented at the first meeting of the Energy Modelling Platform for Europe (EMP-E). The event was organised by the REEEM project as part of the dissemination Deliverables and held in Brussels, on May 17th and 18th 2017, at the premises of the European Commission’s DG Research and Innovation. Part of the results was also presented at the 14th International Conference on the European Energy Market [28].

6.1. Results from TIMES Pan-EU

One of the key outputs of the model are the net electricity capacity investments per energy carrier. These are shown in Figure 14 in terms of power (GW), for the whole EU out of illustrative purposes. Similar figures are available for every country.

Figure 14. Net electricity capacity for EU28 in Pilot 1 and Pilot 2.

Another key output, directly fed as input to the environmental models EMC2, EcoSense and EVA, is the CO2 emissions by country every year. In Figure 15, the emissions in 2050 are shown.

Figure 15. CO2 emissions in 2050 as a percentage of 1990 CO2 emissions.

The main sources of input data for TIMES Pan-EU in the pilot are:

- Eurostat for the calibration of the base years (2010 and 2015) [23];
- [29–31] for the general assumptions;
- [32–34] for the sector-specific assumptions.

6.2. Results from NEWAGE

One of the main outputs of NEWAGE is the GDP projection for the EU. This is to be fed as input to the TIMES Pan-EU model in REEEM, but was not in the pilot exercise. The results for the case *eutrade* (Pilot 1) and *eunotrade* (Pilot 2) are shown in Figure 16. Pilot 2, where the decarbonisation target is reached without cooperation between the countries, is slightly economically disadvantageous, as intuitively expected.

Figure 16. EU GDP.

6.3. Results from EMC2 and EcoSense

EMC2 first processes the results of TIMES Pan-EU relative to nationally aggregated emissions of various pollutants and operates a spatial allocation. Figure 17 and Figure 18 show the resulting maps of spatially allocated GHG emissions in 2050 for Pilot 1 and Pilot 2, respectively.

Figure 17. Spatially allocated GHG emissions in 2050 as resulting from Pilot 1.

Figure 18. Spatially allocated GHG emissions in 2050 as resulting from Pilot 2.

Figure 19 shows the impact of the emissions by electricity and heat generation technologies on health, in terms of disability-adjusted life years (DALYs) for the whole EU.

Figure 19. Health impacts of emissions by electricity and heat generation in EU28 (DALYs).

Also the health damage costs, in economic terms, are available, potentially to be fed as a feedback input to TIMES Pan-EU. These are provided in Figure 20.

Figure 20. Health damage cost of emissions from electricity and heat generation in the EU28 (€2010 undiscounted).

High resolution maps of the spatially allocated health impacts and health damage costs are also available, of the same kind as those of Figure 17 and Figure 18.

6.4. Results from the Cordex Database

From the Cordex Database, maps of the change of heating and cooling demand in the EU in 2050 compared to 2010 were obtained, assuming RCP2.6 as a climate change scenario. The values of heating and cooling demand may be fed as input to TIMES Pan-EU. In Figure 21, the map for the heating demand is shown for illustrative purposes. An analogue map for the cooling demand is available. This is only one of the many outputs of REEEM Task 5.1, dealing with the nexus between climate, land use, water use and energy.

Figure 21. Map of change in heating demand.

6.5. Lessons learnt from the pilot thought experiment

The pilot thought experiment fulfilled its purpose in two ways. First of all, it led the modelling teams to:

- *Create standard excel templates to report the inputs and outputs of their models.* These were shared among all the teams, creating a common understanding of the terminology and level of aggregation of the information. In addition, scripts were created to automatically import the numerical data from the excel templates to the REEEM Pathways Database.
- *Identify and establish the links between the models.* The links may be of two kinds: a model may need one specific output of another model as input (e.g. EMC2 needs the nationally aggregated emissions resulting from the TIMES Pan-EU model as input); or two models may have similar inputs, therefore needing harmonisation.
- *Collect and discuss the insights deriving from pathways differing only by one controllable parameter, depending on the future:* an 80% decarbonisation target for the EU as a whole or for each individual country separately. It might be expected that similar messages come from the two pathways F1_TI1_P1 and F2_TI1_P1.

Secondly, it unveiled a few challenges, inherent to modelling frameworks with a large and multi-sectoral model suit, to be addressed in the continuation of the modelling activity:

1. The modelling teams have different backgrounds and consequently different understanding of the terminology employed when modelling, including the naming of inputs and outputs.

2. Each REEEM pathway is meant to tell a plausible and consistent story about how the future of the EU energy system might unfold, with respect to: the energy system itself, the macroeconomic setting around it, the development of energy technologies, the behaviour of the consumers, the impacts on health and on the ecosystems, the Life Cycle consumption of resources, the security of energy supply, the nexus between Climate, Land, Energy and Water and others. Therefore, whenever defining a pathway, the competent working group in REEEM must keep an eye both on defining the broad context in an internally consistent way and collecting assumptions on all the numerous models.
3. When some of the input assumptions of two models are similar, they need to be harmonised. However, they might have different levels of spatial or temporal aggregation in the two models. Therefore, the question of how to disaggregate or aggregate the inputs when transferring them from one model to the other arises.
4. Some of the outputs of some models may be similar. E.g. both TIMES Pan-EU and MESSAGE may give results on the annual emissions in Lithuania. The outputs may have different numerical values due to the different level of detail and few different elements considered in the two models. Ways of showing effectively where the difference comes from and explaining it to the general audience must be sought for.

These challenges bred the debates during the project's General Assemblies, the public workshops and the dissemination activities (e.g. the Energy Modelling Platform for Europe). They also informed the ongoing work in REEEM on the pathway definition. This report is a result of such debates and focused on addressing challenges 1 and 2. Challenges 3 and 4, related more to the modelling activity, shall be addressed in the REEEM Integrated Impact Reports (due on January 2018 and July 2019) and other similar REEEM deliverables.

7. Conclusions

This report described the process for the definition of EU energy transition pathways developed in REEEM and introduced the structure, main assumptions and preliminary impact indicators of the first pathways defined. Throughout the report, the challenges of defining pathways with a large and multi-sectoral modelling framework are pinpointed and ways to overcome them proposed. The report delivered insights and messages for different groups of readers.

General audience. It presents the methodological and modelling basis of the REEEM project in a transparent manner, explaining the pathway definition process step-by-step and proposing a short reference glossary. It also highlights the 1) novelty of the approach, lying in its applicability for a large and highly integrated modelling framework and the 2) relevance of the approach, lying in the comprehensive view it offers on the interdependencies between sectors.

European Commission. It highlights the links with the Energy Union and the SET-Plan, with its reference to the SET-Plan progress in one of the key steps of the pathway definition process (the choice of the technology issues). Here an interaction point is opened between REEEM and the Commission on which technological development tracks it may be relevant to analyse and how their role could be modelled.

Energy modellers and modelling projects. It delivers a scientifically sound and repeatable process to define pathways for a multi-model and multi-sectoral analysis. The process is grounded in theory and in the experiences shared in literature. The challenges along the process are identified and discussed.

Stakeholders. It pinpoints the steps in the REEEM activities where interaction with the stakeholders is essential and describes how it is meant to occur. This is meant to contribute to ongoing discussions in literature about the necessity of involving stakeholders in energy planning processes.

The REEEM partners and modellers. The report is meant as a guide for the modelling teams towards the creation of the REEEM integrated modelling framework and the continuation of the quantitative analyses. Specifically, it delivers:

- A standardised process to be followed for the definition of all pathways in REEEM;
- Indication of the entry points of different working groups and modelling teams;
- A view of the modelling framework and its different configurations along the activities of the project;
- The first two futures, the technology issues and the assumptions on the first two pathways;
- A preliminary list of pathway diagnostics indicators and a list of the challenges emerged when trying to structure it, to be addressed during the next internal workshops and General Assemblies;
- A reflection on the insights obtained from the Pilot thought experiment and how they indicated the way forward.

Appendix A

Table A1. Population projections for the EU28 countries in Million people. Source: [19].

Country\year	2015	2020	2025	2030	2035	2040	2045	2050
Austria	8.6	8.8	9.1	9.3	9.5	9.6	9.7	9.7
Belgium	11.3	11.9	12.4	12.9	13.5	14.0	14.4	14.8
Bulgaria	7.2	7.0	6.7	6.5	6.2	6.1	5.9	5.8
Cyprus	0.8	0.9	0.9	0.9	0.9	1.0	1.0	1.0
Czech Republic	10.5	10.7	10.7	10.8	10.8	10.9	11.0	11.1
Germany	81.2	80.6	80.3	79.7	78.8	77.7	76.2	74.5
Denmark	5.7	5.8	5.9	6.1	6.2	6.3	6.4	6.4
Estonia	1.3	1.3	1.2	1.2	1.2	1.2	1.1	1.1
Spain	46.4	45.7	45.0	44.5	44.4	44.7	45.1	45.6
Finland	5.5	5.6	5.8	5.9	6.0	6.1	6.1	6.2
France	66.4	67.8	69.2	70.5	71.8	72.9	73.7	74.4
Greece	10.9	10.7	10.4	10.1	9.8	9.6	9.3	9.1
Hungary	9.9	9.8	9.7	9.7	9.6	9.5	9.4	9.3
Croatia	4.2	4.2	4.1	4.1	4.0	4.0	3.9	3.8
Ireland	4.6	4.6	4.6	4.6	4.6	4.7	4.8	5.0
Italy	60.8	62.1	63.1	64.2	65.3	66.3	66.9	67.0
Lithuania	2.9	2.6	2.4	2.2	2.1	2.0	1.9	1.9
Luxembourg	0.6	0.6	0.7	0.8	0.9	0.9	1.0	1.1
Latvia	2.0	1.9	1.7	1.6	1.5	1.5	1.5	1.5
Malta	0.4	0.4	0.4	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5
Netherlands	16.9	17.2	17.4	17.6	17.7	17.6	17.5	17.4
Poland	38.0	38.4	38.0	37.5	36.8	36.2	35.5	34.8
Portugal	10.4	10.1	9.9	9.8	9.6	9.4	9.1	8.8
Romania	19.9	19.7	19.4	19.0	18.7	18.4	18.2	17.9
Sweden	9.7	10.2	10.6	11.0	11.4	11.8	12.1	12.5
Slovenia	2.1	2.1	2.1	2.1	2.1	2.1	2.1	2.1
Slovakia	5.4	5.4	5.4	5.3	5.2	5.1	5.0	4.9
United Kingdom	64.9	66.9	68.8	70.6	72.3	74.0	75.7	77.3
EU-28	508.5	513.0	515.9	519.0	521.4	524.1	525.0	525.5

Table A2. GDP projections for the EU28 countries in 2010M€. Source: [19].

Country\year	2015	2020	2025	2030	2035	2040	2045	2050
Austria	310.2	339.8	364.3	392.5	424.9	460.0	495.5	528.6
Belgium	376.6	413.3	438.7	477.3	529.6	587.5	645.5	705.8
Bulgaria	40.6	48.2	52.2	55.7	59.7	63.1	66.6	69.7

<i>Cyprus</i>	16.0	18.1	19.1	20.6	23.2	25.7	28.4	31.1
<i>Czech Republic</i>	150.8	167.5	182.2	200.2	216.7	234.6	254.0	273.6
<i>Germany</i>	2782.6	2927.9	3077.2	3186.4	3316.0	3485.1	3662.9	3830.7
<i>Denmark</i>	244.9	280.0	307.6	333.0	360.5	392.2	428.8	468.8
<i>Estonia</i>	18.8	20.7	22.6	24.5	26.4	28.2	29.9	31.4
<i>Spain</i>	994.5	1078.0	1167.0	1263.4	1361.1	1409.4	1466.7	1572.3
<i>Finland</i>	190.6	198.3	209.4	225.6	246.7	268.4	290.5	311.5
<i>France</i>	2006.2	2135.8	2289.6	2466.5	2696.6	2933.8	3207.5	3506.8
<i>Greece</i>	161.9	162.8	167.0	179.0	196.6	206.7	216.1	224.9
<i>Hungary</i>	100.0	110.3	122.4	135.2	145.6	154.5	164.9	176.7
<i>Croatia</i>	40.4	43.3	45.5	48.8	53.9	58.6	63.1	67.3
<i>Ireland</i>	197.4	212.2	227.5	248.7	270.6	290.0	310.9	341.6
<i>Italy</i>	1505.1	1597.7	1679.2	1782.4	1920.2	2058.4	2206.6	2377.1
<i>Lithuania</i>	34.1	37.3	39.0	39.0	40.8	43.5	46.9	50.0
<i>Luxembourg</i>	47.9	54.3	61.7	70.9	81.8	93.4	105.2	116.7
<i>Latvia</i>	22.4	26.1	28.6	30.4	32.7	35.1	37.3	39.2
<i>Malta</i>	8.1	8.9	9.8	10.7	11.9	13.0	14.1	15.1
<i>Netherlands</i>	624.2	661.8	688.7	720.2	764.5	815.5	869.9	932.5
<i>Poland</i>	393.4	454.1	518.8	575.6	626.2	674.6	712.5	741.5
<i>Portugal</i>	165.0	179.2	190.2	200.9	210.1	217.6	224.2	231.0
<i>Romania</i>	147.5	164.9	181.1	194.2	208.2	224.2	241.6	259.0
<i>Sweden</i>	409.0	449.2	498.4	553.0	616.6	687.5	762.7	838.0
<i>Slovenia</i>	35.5	38.9	41.6	44.4	47.4	50.1	53.1	56.4
<i>Slovakia</i>	71.8	82.1	95.7	108.7	116.6	121.3	125.6	129.4
<i>United Kingdom</i>	1977.8	2091.6	2231.1	2427.3	2679.9	2973.4	3282.9	3589.2
EU-28	13073	14002	14956	16015	17285	18605	20014	21516

Appendix B

Table B1. Current list of REEEM primary indicators.

Indicator	Suggested dimensions		
	Eco.	Env.	Soc.
Global			
GDP by country	X		
Competitiveness – RCA	X		
Competitiveness – RWTS	X		
EU Energy system			
Prices of energy carriers	X		
System costs (capital, variable O&M, fixed O&M)	X		
CO2 prices	X		
Electricity exchange - net imports	X		
Investments in new capacity by sector, energy carrier and technology	X		
Primary energy consumption		X	
Final energy consumption by sector		X	
Electricity and heat production of industrial and public power plants and CHP plants by sector, energy carrier and technology (at regional, national and municipality level)		X	
Externalities			
External cost (avoidance cost) for biodiversity losses due to air pollution	X	X	
Spatially allocated health damage costs by heat and electricity production	X	X	
Emissions			
Nationally aggregated and spatially allocated emissions of GHGs (CO2 equivalent), CO, PM2.5, PM10, SO2/Sox, NO2/NOx, NVMOC by heat and electricity production processes		X	
Climate			
Spatially allocated change in heating and cooling demand by 2030 and 2050 (degrees-day and %)		X	
Water			
Water availability for power generation		X	
Ecosystem services			
Biodiversity losses (potentially disappeared fractions of species) due to air pollution		X	
Industrial wood yield		X	

Bioenergy yield		x	
Recreation		x	
Carbon stock		x	
Habitat		x	
Life Cycle			
Freshwater, marine and terrestrial eutrophication		x	
Freshwater, marine and terrestrial ecotoxicity		x	
Water, metal resources and fossil resources depletion		x	
Agricultural, urban and natural land occupation		x	
Ozone depletion		x	
Photochemical ozone formation		x	
Particulate matter formation		x	
Single substances emissions and resource consumption over life cycle		x	
Impact of acidification on terrestrial and freshwater ecosystems		x	
Health			
Spatially allocated health impacts by heat and electricity production in DALYs			x
Other			
Job creation	x		x
Distributional impacts	x		x

Table B2. Current list of REEEM secondary indicators.

Indicator	Source	Suggested dimensions		
		Eco.	Env.	Soc.
LCOE		x		
CO2 emissions reduction compared to 1990 levels			x	
Primary energy savings compared to baseline projection	[20]		x	
ETS emissions and carbon prices over time	[20]	x		
Energy intensities by sector (industry, agriculture, tertiary, household, transport, non-energy use)	[20–22]	x		
Shares of environmental and labour taxes in total tax revenues from taxes and social contributions (Implicit tax rate on energy)	[23,26]	x		x
Energy efficiency index by sector	[26]		x	

Efficiency of energy conversion and distribution	[21,22]		x	
CCS Indicator (% of electricity from power plants applying CCS)	[21]		x	
Share of renewable energy sources in final energy consumption, by technology	[20–24,26]		x	
Intensity of goods transport and of passenger transport (Pkm/GJ)	[20,21,24]		x	
Greenhouse gas emissions intensity of energy consumption	[20,21,23]		x	
Soil area where acidification exceeds critical load	[22]		x	
Forest area as a proportion of total land area	[27]		x	
Proportion of important sites for terrestrial and freshwater biodiversity that are covered by protected areas, by ecosystem type	[27]		x	
Species diversity and landscape quality	[24]		x	

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